

Synthesis of some Sulphur Heterocycles as Fungicides

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Manuscript received 27 June 1974; revised 5 November 1974; accepted 13 December 1974.

Reaction of *N*-substituted thioureas and bromo-cyano-ethyl acetate yields 2-imino-3-substituted-4-amino-5-carbethoxy- Δ^4 -thiazolines. The amino-thiazolines on further reaction with different aryl-isothiocyanates afford the corresponding thioureas. Some 1, 4-disubstituted thiosemicarbazides yield upon reaction with monochloroacetic acid, 2-arylaminoimino-3-aryl-4-thiazolidinones. These compounds are screened for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*.

As recently reported¹, thiazolines and thiazolidinones owe their antitubercular² anti-radiation³, nematocidal⁴ and fungicidal-activities^{5, 6} due to the presence of -N-C-S grouping. This active moiety is present in the title compounds. On the basis of these results, further investigations were carried out in this field.

N-Arylthioureas were condensed separately with bromocyano ethylacetate to give 2-imino-3-aryl-4-amino-5-carbethoxy- Δ^4 -thiazolines⁷. These amino thiazolines were converted into unsymmetrical thioureas⁸ by the reaction of arylisothiocyanates. Some 1, 4-disubstituted thiosemicarbazides, on condensation with monochloroacetic acid afforded 2-arylaminoimino-3-aryl-4-thiazolidinones. There are several possible alternatives regarding the formation of products which are shown in Schemes 1 and 2. The structures of thiazolidinones were confirmed by the hydrolysis of thiazolidinones and thiohydantoin obtained. The condensation product

was not hydrolysed by glacial acetic acid, aqueous sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid, but, it was hydrolysed by moderately strong sulphuric acid giving a crystalline product, which was identified as 3-phenyl-2, 4-thiazolidine-dione (VI).

Isolation of the compound (VI) after hydrolysis clearly indicates that compound is thiazolidinone of structure (II) rather than thiohydantoin, because only structure (II) can give 3-phenyl-2, 4 thiazolidindione.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected.

2-Imino-3-phenetyl-4-amino-5-carbethoxy- Δ^4 -thiazolines⁷ : *N*-Phenethylthiourea (0.1 mole) was dissolved in acetone (15 ml) and bromocyanoethylacetate (0.1 mole) was added slowly with continuous shaking at room temperature. The whole mixture was refluxed for 2 hr. The product which separated was collected and dissolved in water, filtered and the filtrate was neutralised with concentrated ammonia. The free base was collected and washed with water and crystallised from ethanol, yield 30% m. p. 160°. Found : C, 55.1; H, 5.8; N, 14.08 C₁₄H₁₇N₃O₃S requires : C, 54.72; H, 5.53; N, 13.68%.

2-Imino-3-(*p*-)bromophenyl-4-amino-5-carbethoxy- Δ^4 -thiazoline⁷ : It was prepared by the reaction of *N*-(*p*-) bromophenylthiourea (0.1 mole) and isolated as described above, m. p. 165°. Found : C, 42.3; H, 3.8; N, 12.38 C₁₂H₁₂N₃BrO₂S requires : C, 42.1; H, 3.5; N, 12.28%.

2-Imino-3-aryl-4-substituted-thiouriedo-5-carbethoxy- Δ^4 -thiazolines : 2-Imino-3-aryl-4-amino-5-carbethoxy- Δ^4 -thiazoline (0.1 mole) was dissolved in ethanol and treated with arylisothiocyanate (0.1 mole) and the mixture was warmed. After half an hour a precipitate separated which was filtered, washed with little ethanol and crystallised from aqueous ethanol. Analysis; m. p. and other relevant data are recorded in Table 1.

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